

An Attempt to Account Quantitatively for the Electroviscous Behaviour of Some Colloidal Ampholytes

B. N. GHOSH

University College of Science & Technology, Calcutta-700 009.

Manuscript received 6 June 1977, accepted 9 July 1977

For Colloidal ampholytes, Smoluchowski's electroviscosity equation has been modified by taking into consideration the contribution of the ampholyte molecules to the specific conductivity of the solution.

EQUATIONS, to suit special cases such as (1) the variation of η_{sp}/C with C , the concentration of the ampholyte when the pH and ionic-strength of the system are kept constant and (2) the variation of η_{sp}/C with S , the concentration of an added strong electrolyte at constant C and pH , have been deduced starting from this modified equation. These equations have been found to agree satisfactorily with the data available in the literature on viscosity measurements of the globular proteins, bovine serum albumin, ribonuclease and β -lactoglobulin at pH corresponding to their isoionic points and also at other values of pH . It follows from the equation on the variation of η_{sp}/C with C that at $Lt_c \rightarrow 0$, the excess of intrinsic viscosity over $Kv/100 = 0.0188$, (where $K = 2.5$ and $v = 0.75$, the specific volume of the protein) is a part of the electroviscous effect and that part is independent of C . In the literature, this excess of intrinsic viscosity has so long been attributed to the hydration of the protein molecules.

In the electroviscous equations of Smoluchowski¹ and Booth² it has been assumed that the colloidal particles act as non-conductors, Briggs³ has expressed doubt on the validity of this assumption with reference to colloidal electrolytes. In a previous publication the author⁴ has pointed out the necessity of taking into consideration the contribution of the colloidal particles to the specific conductivity term in the electroviscosity equation of Smoluchowski.

The Smoluchowski equation may be written as follows :—

$$\eta_{sp} = K \frac{Cv}{100} \left[1 + \frac{1}{\eta a^2 \lambda} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \dots \dots (1)$$

where η_{sp} denotes the specific viscosity of the solution, K is a constant and according to Einstein it is equal to 2.5 for spherical particles, C , the concentration of the colloid in gram per 100 ml of the solution, v , the specific volume of the colloid, 'a', the radius of the particles, ζ , their electrokinetic potential and D , η and λ are the dielectric constant, viscosity and specific conductivity respectively of the dispersion medium.

It has been shown by the author in previous publications⁵⁻⁷ that λ the specific conductivity of the solution of a colloidal electrolyte is made up of two parts, one part $\theta\lambda_s$ contributed by the colloidal particles and the other part $(1-\theta)\lambda_i$ contributed by the intermicellar solution (i.e., the dispersion medium) and they are related by the equation ;

$$\lambda = \theta\lambda_s + (1-\theta)\lambda_i \dots \dots (2)$$

where λ_s is constant for a well-dialysed pure sol and represents the specific conductivity of the double layer at the plane of contact with an electrode of the conductivity cell, θ , the fraction of the surface per unit area of an electrode covered by the diffuse double layers of the particles and θ is equal to $C/(K_0+C)$ where K_0 is a constant and C the concentration (unit arbitrary) of the colloidal particles.

Derivation of the equations :

Substituting the values of λ and θ in equation (1) and putting $A = \frac{1}{\eta a^2} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2$ we get the following equation :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{v}{100} \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2(C+K_0)}{\lambda_s(C+K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s)} \right] \dots \dots (3)$$

In a sol, highly purified by dialysis, λ_i is much smaller than λ_s and if the solution is diluted with water then it follows from equation (3) that η_{sp}/C will increase as C decreases, since all the other terms remain constant.

If a strong electrolyte, in small quantity, is added to the solution then ζ and λ_s diminish slightly but λ_i increases sharply. As the concentration of the added electrolyte is increased gradually λ_i increases more and more and when the level of concentration reached is such that C in the denominator of equation (3) becomes negligible compared to $K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s$ then equation (3) assumes the form

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{v}{100} \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2}{\lambda_i} + \frac{A\zeta^2}{K_0\lambda_i} C \right] \dots \dots (4)$$

$$= K \frac{v}{100} \left[1 + A_1 + \beta C \right] \dots \dots (5)$$

where $A_1 = A\zeta^2/\lambda_i$ and $\beta = A\zeta^2/K_0\lambda_i$

If the concentration of the added electrolyte is now fixed and only C is increased then η_{sp}/C will increase linearly with C , since all the other terms in equation (5) remain constant. It is to be noted that since the constants A_1 and β are determined from viscosity data they may include a proportionality constant.

Variation of η_{sp}/C with electrolyte concentration at constant C :

Let $(\eta_{sp}/C)_0$ and $(\eta_{sp}/C)_s$ denote respectively the values of η_{sp}/C when the concentration of the added electrolyte is zero and S respectively and let their ratio $(\eta_{sp}/C)_s : (\eta_{sp}/C)_0$ be denoted by R . Then an equation connecting the variation of R with S over a limited range of the latter, may be deduced from equation (3) in the following way :

*Let ζ change to $\zeta(1-aS)$ and λ_1 change to $\lambda_1(1+hS)$ as the concentration of the added electrolyte changes from zero to S . Now putting $A_0 = A(C+K_0)$ in equation (3) we may write as follows :

$$R = K \frac{v}{100} \left[1 + \frac{A_0 \zeta^2 (1-aS)^2}{C \lambda_s + K_0 \lambda_1 (1+hS)} \right] : K \frac{v}{100} \left[1 + \frac{A_0 \zeta^2}{C \lambda_s + K_0 \lambda_1} \right]$$

$$= \left[\frac{B + (K_0 \lambda_1 h - 2A_0 a \zeta^2) S}{(H + K_0 \lambda_1 h S)} \times \frac{H}{B} \right]$$

$$= \left[1 - \frac{mS}{m_0 + S} \right] \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where terms in $(S)^2$ have been neglected and $B = (C \lambda_s + K_0 \lambda_1 + A_0 \zeta^2)$.

$$H = (C \lambda_s + K_0 \lambda_1),$$

$$m = \left[\frac{(K_0 \lambda_1 h / H) - (K_0 \lambda_1 h - 2A_0 a \zeta^2) / B}{(K_0 \lambda_1 h) / H} \right]$$

$$\text{and } m_0 = H / K_0 \lambda_1 h$$

In equation (6) m and m_0 are constants, since all the terms contained in them remain constant when S alone is varied.

Isoionic point and the application of the equations :

The application of the equations mentioned above to proteins at their isoionic point may be questioned since at this point their net charge is zero or nearly so. It may be pointed out in this connection that since the charged sites on a protein molecule are separated by a distance^{8,9}, each of them will have its own ion atmosphere and there will be a difference, of potential, say ζ , between the charged site and its ion atmosphere in the solution.

The average of ζ will be zero but the average of ζ^2 will always have a positive value[†]. Therefore, theoretically there can be no objection against the use of the aforesaid equations on any protein even at its isoionic point.

Source of data and observation of the investigators

Tanford and Buzzell⁸ have investigated the viscous properties of bovine serum albumin (BSA) solutions at different values of pH and ionic strength. Crystalline bovine serum albumin, obtained from Armour and Co, is dissolved in water and the solutions are deionised and brought to isoionic pH by passing them through ion-exchange column as described by Dintzis¹⁰. The pH of a solution is adjusted by adding appropriate amounts of HCl or KOH and its ionic strength is fixed by adding the required amounts of KCl. The ionic strength has been defined as the total concentration of an electrolyte (all univalent) and according to them it is a compromise between two extreme procedures, "that of counting a protein molecule with a net charge of Z , as a Z valent ion, which because of the wide separation of charges, is clearly inappropriate and that of not counting the protein charges at all."

The viscosity and density of the solutions have been measured at 25° with proper care. They have observed that at constant pH and ionic strength η_{sp}/C varies linearly with C and that the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ found by extrapolating the line to $C=0$, at the isoionic point, is practically constant, $[\eta] = 0.0369 \pm 0.0010$ for all ionic strengths except $\mu=0$, but at $\mu=0$, $[\eta] = 0.0406$. It has also been observed that at ionic strength above 0.01 change of pH between 4.3 and 7.3 affects $[\eta]$ only slightly. Its average value in these ranges of pH and ionic strength is 0.0371 ± 0.0009 .

The aforesaid authors^{1,1} have also investigated at 25° the viscous properties of ribonuclease over a wide range of pH and ionic strength. Crystalline ribonuclease of bovine origin obtained from Armour & Co. is dissolved in water and the solutions are deionised and brought to isoionic point by passing them through ion-exchange column. Their pH and ionic strength are adjusted at the desired levels in the same way as in the case of BSA. They have found that at constant pH and ionic strength η_{sp}/C varies linearly with C and that no significant change in $[\eta]$ occurs between pH 5.9 and pH 11 at ionic strength above 0.01. The mean value of $[\eta]$ in these ranges of pH and ionic strength, with its root mean square deviation is 0.033 ± 0.0004 . Their data are recorded in the Tables 1, 2, 5 and 6 of this paper.

The electroviscous properties of β -lactoglobulin have been investigated by Briggs and Hanig^{1,2} at 25°. Crystalline β -lactoglobulin prepared by a modification of Palmer's method has been recrystallised twice. Since this protein crystallises at its iso-electric point (pH 5.18) after prolonged dialysis against distilled water no further purification has been considered necessary for the preparation of isoionic solution.

* Slight variation in λ_s is completely overshadowed by the variation in λ_1 and so the former can be neglected. The linear variation of ζ and λ_1 with S , assumed above, is expected to hold good as S is small.

† Similar views have also been expressed by previous authors.^{8,9}

On the acid side of the isoionic point, pH of the solutions has been adjusted by adding HCl, and on the alkaline side by adding NaOH. The salt content of the solutions has been adjusted by adding the required amount of NaCl.

Their data taken from the Tables 2a, 2b and 2c of their paper are recorded in the Tables 3, 4, 7 and 8 of this paper.

Notes on data recorded in the tables.

In Table 1 are recorded the data on measurement of viscosity of bovine serum albumin (BSA) at 25° at the isoionic point (pH about 5.0) and also at pH 8.5 by Tanford and Buzzell⁸. These data are taken from Table 1 and Figure 1 of their paper.

In column 2 of Table 1, C represents the concentration in grams of BSA per 100 ml. of the solution. The other terms have the same significance as discussed already.

TABLE 1
INCREASE OF η_{sp}/C WITH THE CONCENTRATION C OF BSA

Miscellaneous	C	Values of η_{sp}/C	
		Observed	Calculated
Isoionic	0	0.0369	0.0368
pH nearly 5.0	0.60	0.0395	0.0393
Ionic strength-0.002	1.30	0.0423	0.0421
Equation used (5)	1.70	0.0438	0.0437
K=2.5	2.58	0.0476	0.0470
V/100=0.0075	3.97	0.0510	0.0504
A ₁ =0.96	4.22	0.0542	0.0538
$\beta=0.213$			
pH 8.5	0	0.0406	0.0406
Ionic strength-0.02	1.10	0.0475	0.0466
Equation used (5)	1.64	0.0512	0.0515
	2.70	0.0579	0.0579
K=2.5	3.43	0.0625	0.0626
V/100=0.0075	4.07	0.0672	0.0667
A ₁ =1.16			
$\beta=0.34$			

In Table 2 are recorded the data of Buzzel and Tanford¹¹ on measurements of viscosity of ribonuclease at 25°, at the isoionic point (pH 9.6) and also at pH 5.9. These data are selected from Table 1 and Figure 1 of their paper. There is a printing error in Figure 1 of their paper in which 4.5 should be read instead of 5.0, on the ordinate. The terms used in Table 2 have the same significance as in Table 1.

In Table 3 of this paper are recorded the data of Briggs and Hanig¹² on measurements of viscosity of β -lactoglobulin at the isoionic point (pH 5.20 approximately) in the presence of 0.05 moles of NaCl per liter. These data have been collected from Table 2c of their paper. Table 4 contains the data of the same authors taken from Table 2a of their paper. In Table 4, m represents the electrophoretic velocity of the protein molecules under unit potential gradient.

TABLE 2
INCREASE OF η_{sp}/C WITH C OF RIBONUCLEASE

Miscellaneous	C	Values of η_{sp}/C	
		Observed	Calculated
Isoionic point	0	0.0327	0.0327
Ionic strength-0.05	1.45	0.0363	0.0363
Equation used (5)	2.07	0.0378	0.0379
K=2.5	2.48	0.0384	0.0388
V/100=0.0075	3.50	0.0416	0.0415
A ₁ =0.74	4.14	0.0426	0.0430
$\beta=0.133$			
pH 5.9	0	0.0332	0.0333
Ionic strength-0.02	0.97	0.0360	0.0363
Equation used (5)	1.56	0.0382	0.0382
K=2.5	2.34	0.0408	0.0407
V/100=0.0075	3.28	0.0434	0.0437
A ₁ =0.77	4.11	0.0461	0.0464
$\beta=0.17$			

The other terms in the Tables 3 and 4 have the same significance as stated already.

TABLE 3
DATA ON η_{sp}/C OF β -LACTOGLOBULIN FOR DIFFERENT VALUES OF C

Miscellaneous	C	η_{sp}	Values of η_{sp}/C	
			Observed	Calculated
Isoionic point	0			0.0378
NaCl-0.05N	0.5	0.0196	0.0392	0.0378
Equation used (3)				
K=2.5	1.0	0.0367	0.0367	0.0378
V/100=0.0075				
A ₁ =1.01	2.0	0.0745	0.0373	0.0378
$\lambda_0=\lambda_1$				

TABLE 4
VARIATION OF η_{sp}/C WITH C OF β -LACTOGLOBULIN AT pH 4.22 ± 0.05

Miscellaneous	C	m × 10 ⁴	η_{sp}	Values of η_{sp}/C	
				Observed	Calculated
NaCl-Nil	0				0.0577
Equation used	0.5	2.12	0.0256	0.0512	0.0521
$\eta_{sp}/C = \left[1 + \frac{6.2}{C+3} \right] (0.0188)$	1.0	1.75	0.0468	0.0468	0.0479
	2.0	1.41	0.0886	0.0443	0.0431

In the Tables 5 and 6 of this paper are recorded the data on the variation of R of BSA and ribonuclease with S at constant protein concentration C. S represents the ionic strength or the total concentration of the added electrolyte and since the solutions of the proteins are at their respective isoionic points no addition of acid or alkali is required to adjust the pH. Therefore, the total concentration is the concentration of KCl required to adjust the ionic strength of the solutions and it is the same as S in equation (6). $[\eta]$ in these tables represents the intrinsic viscosity. In Table 6 the mean values of $[\eta]$ have been recorded excepting the first one.

TABLE 5
VARIATION OF R WITH S, BSA CONCENTRATION—
3g. PER 100 ml.

Miscellaneous	S	[η]	η_{sp}/C	Values of R	
				Observed	Calculated
*Isoionic point pH=5.0 nearly C=3 per cent	0	0.0406	0.0568	1.0	1.0
Equation used (6)	0.001	0.0362	0.0512	0.902	0.902
	0.010	0.0369	0.0469	0.861	0.869
		0.0361	0.0466	0.820	0.820
m=0.199					
m ₀ =0.00103	0.085	0.0382	0.0457	0.805	0.804

* According to the authors* pH increases from 5.0 to about 5.6 as S changes from 0 to 0.15.

TABLE 6
VARIATION OF R WITH S, RIBONUCLEASE—3g. PER 100 ml.

Miscellaneous	S	[η]	η_{sp}/C	Variation of R	
				Observed	Calculated
Isoionic point pH 9.6	0	0.0396	0.0447	1.0	1.0
C=3 per cent	0.001	0.038	0.0432	0.966	0.966
Equation used (6)	0.01	0.038	0.0411	0.919	0.919
m=0.096	0.02	0.038	0.0408	0.913	0.912
m ₀ =0.00181	0.05	0.038	0.0405	0.906	0.907

In the Tables 7 and 8 are recorded the data of measurements of Briggs and Hanig¹¹ on viscosity of β -lactoglobulin at different concentrations S of NaCl, the pH and the protein concentration C of the solutions being maintained constant at the desired levels.

Discussions

For the globular proteins mentioned in this paper $K=2.5$ and their specific volume[†] $V=0.75$, so in equation (1) $Kv/100=0.0188$. The data recorded in the Tables 1 and 2 show that η_{sp}/C of BSA and ribonuclease increase with the increase of C and the agreement between the values of η_{sp}/C observed and those calculated by using equation (5) is quite satisfactory at values of pH corresponding to the isoionic points and also at other values of pH. It is to be noted that at $C \rightarrow 0$ the excess of intrinsic viscosity over 0.0183 is given by the expression

$$0.0188A_1 = 0.0188 \left[\frac{\xi^2}{\eta_a^2 \lambda_1} \left(\frac{D}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right]$$

which is a part of the electroviscous effect independent of C. In the literature this is usually attributed to the hydration of the protein molecules. Equation (5) thus leads to the conclusion that in the case of the globular proteins the intrinsic viscosity in excess of 0.0188, so long attributed to hydration, is but a part of the electroviscous effect.

The data on β -lactoglobulin, at the isoionic point in the presence of 0.05 N NaCl, recorded in Table 3 show that η_{sp}/C remains practically constant when C is varied. The data fit the equation $\eta_{sp}/C=0.0188$

$[1 + A\xi^2/\lambda_1$ where $A\xi^2/\lambda_1=1.01$. It may be pointed out that equation (3) assumes the aforesaid form when $\lambda_2=\lambda_1$. It may, therefore, be concluded that at the isoionic point of β -lactoglobulin $\lambda_2=\lambda_1$ nearly when the NaCl content of the solution is 0.05 N.

The data recorded in Table 4 show that in the absence of NaCl and at pH 4.22 ± 0.05 , η_{sp}/C of β -lactoglobulin decreases as C increases. This is just the opposite of what has been observed in the case of ESA and ribonuclease and is to be attributed to the absence of NaCl so that in equation (3) λ_1 is much less than λ_2 and C in the numerator is negligible compared to K_0 . Equation (3) then assumes the following approximate form which fits the data,

$$\eta_{sp}/C = 0.0188 \left[1 + \frac{6.2}{C+3} \right].$$

It may be noticed that m, the electrophoretic mobility, recorded in Table 4 decreases markedly as C increases. This marked decrease in m cannot be accounted for by the increase in viscosity caused by the increase of C. The mobility data obviously require surface conductance or elaborate relaxation correction¹⁴. Therefore, based on such uncorrected data, Briggs remarks on the validity of the electroviscosity equation of Smoluchowski are not of much significance.

The data on isoionic solutions of BSA and ribonuclease recorded in the Tables 5 and 6 show that for different values of S, the observed values of R agree satisfactorily with those calculated by using equation (6).

The data recorded in the Tables 7 and 8 also show that the variation of R of β -lactoglobulin with S of NaCl can be accounted for quantitatively by

TABLE 7
VARIATION OF R OF β -LACTOGLOBULIN AT pH 4.22 ± 0.05

Miscellaneous	S	η_{sp}	Values of R	
			Observed	Calculated
C=0.5 per cent	0	0.0256	1.0	1.0
Equation used (6)	0.0005	0.0237	0.926	0.895
m=0.26	0.001	0.0217	0.848	0.851
m ₀ =0.0074	0.002	0.0206	0.805	0.810
	0.005	0.0196	0.766	0.774
	0.01	0.0193	0.754	0.758
C=1 per cent	0	0.0468	1.0	1.0
Equation used (6)	0.0005	0.0451	0.963	0.948
	0.001	0.0430	0.919	0.919
m=0.19	0.002	0.0417	0.891	0.886
	0.005	0.0396	0.846	0.850
m ₀ =0.00134	0.01	0.0390	0.833	0.832
C=2 per cent	0	0.0886	1.0	1.0
Equation used (6)	0.0005	0.0870	0.982	0.975
	0.001	0.0847	0.956	0.956
m=0.187	0.002	0.0823	0.929	0.928
m ₀ =0.00324	0.005	0.0789	0.891	0.887
	0.01	0.0761	0.859	0.859

† Varying values from 0.71 to 0.75 are reported in the literature.

TABLE 8
 VARIATION OF R OF β -LACTOGLOBULIN AT pH 6.60 ± 0.05

Miscellaneous	S	η_{sp}	Values of R	
			Observed	Calculated
C=0.57 per cent	0	0.0327	1.0	1.0
Equation used (6)	0.001	0.0262	0.801	0.802
	0.002	0.0237	0.725	0.740
$m=0.38$	0.005	0.0224	0.685	0.679
$m_0=0.00092$	0.01	0.0213	0.651	0.652
C=1.15 per cent	0	0.0582	1.0	1.0
Equation used (6)	0.001	0.0513	0.881	0.881
$m=0.275$	0.002	0.0486	0.835	0.834
$m_0=0.00131$	0.005	0.0458	0.787	0.782
	0.01	0.0440	0.756	0.757

equation (6). It may be pointed out here that when S is very small, say $0.0005 M$, any adsorption of it by the protein lowers its value still further. If this lower value of S were known and used in equation (6) the agreement in this region would have improved appreciably. At pH 4.22 ± 0.05 three concentrations of β -lactoglobulin have been used and it may be noticed that m_0 in equation (6) increases as C increases. This is in agreement with the theory, since $m_0 = (C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_i)/K_0\lambda_i h$ and so it should increase as C increases. Similar remarks apply to the two solutions of β -lactoglobulin at pH

6.60 ± 0.05 . It may be pointed out that only the first order (i.e., the primary) electroviscous effect is operative in the range of protein concentration discussed above.

References

1. M. VON SMOLUCHOWSKI, *Kolloid. Z.*, 1916, 18, 194.
2. F. BOOTH, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1950, A203 538.
3. D. R. BRIGGS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, 45, 866.
4. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 881.
5. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 359.
6. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 565.
7. B. N. GHOSH, A. C. S. Symposium Series, Colloidal Dispersions and Micellar Behaviour, 1975, 9, 316.
8. C. TANFORD and J. G. BUZZELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1936, 60, 225.
9. E. J. COHN and J. T. EDSELL, *Proteins, Amino acids and Peptides*, A.C. S. Monograph Series No. 90, 1943, Chapter 20, p. 444.
10. H. M. DENTZIS, Ph.D., *Thesis*. Harvard University, 1952.
11. J. G. BUZZELL and C. TENFORD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 1204.
12. D. R. BRIGGS and M. HANIG, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1944, 48, 1.
13. A. H. PALMER, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, 104, 359.
14. P. H. WIERSEMA, A. L. LOEB and J. TH. G. OVERBERG, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1968, 22, 78.